

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D9.4

Pilot courses and staff exchange provided

WP9 – Training

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Executive Summary

The CORBEL training curriculum is based on a competency profile (D9.1 - CORBEL Refined organisational competency framework needed by distributed RIs at 3 development stages¹) and the gap analysis that was completed based on it. The main target audience of the training programme is technical operators of biological and medical research infrastructures (BMS RIs). CORBEL organises the following types of training activities: webinars, face-to-face courses and staff programme (includes knowledge exchange workshops, staff visits and fellowships).

The present deliverable reports on the online version of the CORBEL competency profile at the EBI competency mapper website² and the training activities carried out since 2017. This includes 20 webinars and 8 face-to-face courses, as well as the 28 staff programme applications received.

CORBEL has successfully delivered different types of training activities and their impact will continue after the end of the project. In addition to the impact on each participant who has gained new knowledge or skills, some of the courses designed within the CORBEL project will continue to be delivered as part of the EMBL (or EMBL-EBI) training programme: *Data visualisation for biology*, *Machine learning for image analysis*; *User research and service design* continues as part of EMBL-EBI and EMBO workshops. The new BMS RI cluster project EOSC-Life³, which will create an open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research, will continue training on, amongst others, ARIA, quality management and Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure (AAI). To further promote the continuation of the project into EOSC-Life, we have delivered a joint webinar series (*Engaging with your community through events and training*), so that the communities within the two projects can benefit from it and that participants learn that many of the CORBEL activities will continue through EOSC-Life. EOSC-Life is a project that brings together 13 BMS RIs, including the ones in CORBEL. EOSC-Life will support the cooperation between RIs and organise training and knowledge exchange events. Many of the BMS RIs have since started their own webinar series. Recordings from the CORBEL webinar series will stay available online through the CORBEL website and the new LifeScience RI.

Project objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) Deliver courses and provide a staff-exchange programme to support sharing of best working practice.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Competency profile

The CORBEL training programme is aimed at technical operators of research infrastructures. The development, delivery and monitoring of the programme is based on a competency profile that was described in D9.1 (CORBEL Refined organisational competency framework needed by distributed RIs

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/154085#.WYGGb4jys2w>

² <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/corbel/1.1>

³ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

at 3 developmental stages)⁴. This competency profile is easily accessible online on the EMBL-EBI competency mapper.

Competency mapper

The Competency mapper is a web-based tool to support the creation and management of competency frameworks for professionals working in life sciences⁵. The competency mapper is being developed by the EMBL-EBI training team. It currently holds five competency frameworks, including the CORBEL one. Competency frameworks were designed to be used by the training communities who developed them, and openly available to anyone who might find them useful, yet all too often they end up buried in a PDF file as part of a project deliverable. This made the EMBL-EBI training team long for a web-based tool that would make these frameworks, and the training associated with them, readily discoverable. We therefore decided to build that tool, and although it is still in the early stages of development we have decided to make it openly available now so that we can seek broad input to improve it and make it as useful as possible to the education and training community at large.

The competency mapper allows versioning of the competency profile. The actual version of the CORBEL competency profile is available at website⁶. Previous versions are accessible at the bottom of the page in a static version. When a new version is created in the competency mapper, release notes are added to describe what changes have been made to the profile and why. The new version includes the attributes (knowledge, skills and behaviors) associated with the competencies of the CORBEL framework.

The competency mapper also allows to add training resources relevant for a competency framework and map them to the specific competencies they contribute to develop. A list of available courses that could cover CORBEL training needs was made available in on-course[®]. This platform is no longer available, the mapping dataset was transferred to the competency mapper to make sure that it is still publicly available. We have curated the dataset and added 310 previously identified training resources to the competency mapper and mapped them to the relevant CORBEL competencies.

CORBEL Staff Programme

In October 2018 the Knowledge Exchange programme was broadened to include more training modalities and rebranded as the CORBEL staff programme. The decision for this change was led by multiple reasons: 1) a reluctance on the host side to organise larger knowledge exchange workshops 2) specific request for smaller more focussed staff visit events 3) request for training that CORBEL was not in a position to deliver.

The staff programme now includes the following training modalities

- Fellowship programme
- Staff visits
- Knowledge Exchange Workshops

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/154085#.XirDlxP7RTY>

⁵ <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>

⁶ <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/corbel/1.1>

The change proved to be very popular, table 1 shows the current number of applications (date 9/03/2020).

Modality	Applications approved
Fellowship	17
Staff visit	9
Knowledge Exchange Workshops	2
Total number	28

Table 1: Overview of Staff Programme Applications

Fellowships

Applications for the following non-CORBEL courses were received and approved by the CORBEL WP9 working group. Some courses have been requested more than once.

- Quality Management Specialist QMF-TÜV
- Introducing DIN EN ISO 9001
- Datenschutzgrundverordnung für Auditoren (General Data Protection Regulation for auditors)
- IMPACT OF E.C. FUNDED RESEARCH - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategies in H2020 Projects provided by the European Academy
- Data Protection Certification Course
- "Module 1-Governance & Organisation" part of RItrain EMMRI
- "Module 2-Strategic Management" part of RItrain EMMRI
- Quality management representative QMR-TÜV
- Pharmacodynamics, Biomarkers and Personalised
- Advanced Communications and PR Management
- An Introduction to Pharmaceutical Regulatory Affairs
- Drug Development, Pharmacokinetics and Imaging
- Project Management for Scientists
- Introductory course on KNIME Analytics Platform
- Business Strategy and Financial Performance

Staff visits

The following staff visits between research infrastructures have been approved:

- Implementation of ARIA system for EU-OS user projects and adaptive extension of ARIA to EU-OS needs [visit from EU-OPENSOURCE to Instruct].
- Knowledge sharing on Communications strategy, Branding, Developing research networks, Working with government ministries, including negotiations towards new membership, Project management, Working with industry and Sustainability and Business plans [visit from Instruct to CERIC].

- To exchange knowledge and experiences within the two RIs (scientific scope, operations, initiatives), to define in more detail synergies and complementarities. To discuss in more detail the implementation of the potential joint activities as outlined in a recently drafted Memorandum of understanding. To learn about the differences between access procedures for RI clients. To update each other on relevant (quality) initiatives and projects/consortia where both EATRIS and EU OPENSURE are involved in [visit from EATRIS to EU-OPENSURE].
- EATRIS seek a leading role in developing lifecycle related training to support the production of FAIR data in the life sciences and recognise the major role played by ELIXIR in this field. The provision of FAIR data has been central to EATRIS mission since its inception [visit from EATRIS to ELIXIR hub].
- Hackathon with the aim of making image data from the Image Data Resource (IDR) accessible through the Galaxy interface [visit from Euro-BioImaging to ELIXIR].
- Use of the facility to perform serial sectioning of different marine model organisms. Visiting RI will soon be equipped with a high pressure freezing machine and getting familiar with this approach is a great opportunity, including sharing and comparing approaches and standard operational procedures [visit from EMBRC to EuroBioImaging].
- Knowledge exchange and use of EMBL cryo-EM facility and development of use case for EMBL [visit of Instruct to EMBL].
- Knowledge exchange around challenges and opportunities of communicating across a distributed, international infrastructure [Instruct to BBMRI-ERIC].

Knowledge Exchange Workshops

The Knowledge exchange workshops were previously reported on in D9.3 - Pilot courses and staff exchange provided⁷.

With the current COVID-19 epidemic we are expecting a number of Staff Programme events not to go ahead, be delayed or converted to remote events.

CORBEL Webinar series

Since 2017 CORBEL has been running an active webinar series. The CORBEL webinar series aims to address challenges and share best practice between biological and medical research infrastructures. The series is aimed at technical operators of RIs and is aligned with the CORBEL competency framework. CORBEL webinars include an audience Q&A session during which attendees can ask questions and make suggestions. All webinars are recorded and available for later viewing on the CORBEL website and the CORBEL YouTube channel⁸.

According to the current schedule, 20 webinars will have been completed by the end of the project, with 28 different speakers from the CORBEL RIs and beyond. A number of speakers gave repeated webinars to show updates to their topic over time (e.g. Michaela Mayrhofer for the Code of Conduct). Combined the webinars together have generated 1420 views on YouTube (as of 2/03/2020).

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/1044177#.Xnh8j9P7TOQ>

⁸ <https://www.corbel-project.eu/webinars>

Date	Title	Nmb Attendees	Conversion
29/05/2017	Identifying and Networking with Industry: How to Market Your Research	16	64.00%
27/06/2017	User Experience Design for more user-friendly applications	21	58.33%
16/01/2018	ARIA - Powering your access management from the cloud	24	64.86%
06/02/2018	Lightweight Service Management for Research Infrastructures: FitSM Approach	46	66.67%
27/02/2018	Data sharing and reuse from clinical trials: principles and recommendations	68	64.15%
17/04/2018	Single sign-on for Life Science services	21	58.33%
22/05/2018	Quality Management in distributed Research Infrastructures	28	62.22%
05/06/2018	Status Update on the Code of Conduct for Health Research Initiative	43	52.44%
10/07/2018	The BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Helpdesk – Personalising ELSI Support	25	54.35%
23/10/2018	West-Life: Lessons learnt from developing a virtual research environment	*	*
06/12/2018	BBMRI-ERIC Quality Management Services for basic and applied research on human specimens	*	*
11/04/2019	A Basic Introduction to Bioimage Analysis	48	60.00%
04/06/2019	Genomics and clinical data at your fingertips with open-source software: transSMART & cBioPortal	30	54.55%
19/06/2019	Towards a GDPR Code of Conduct for Health Research: where are we today?	43	36.44%**
03/12/2019	How to make your event successful and eligible for EU funding: Event management for Research Infrastructures [^]	21	63.64%
19/03/2020	Practical Tips for Stepping Up Your Science Communications [^]	100	65.36%
26/03/2020	Data-integration platform for cancer research: cBioportal demo	37	68.52%
27/03/2020	Course design and delivery: guidance and tips for impactful training ^{^#}	55	69.62%
TBC	Best practice in training and communication ^{^#}		
21/04/2020	The BBMRI ELSI Services across the Nodes & BMS RIs		
Analytics across the series		39.13	60.22%

*Table 2: Overview of the CORBEL webinar series. *for these webinars the analytics are unretrievable ** Webinar had to be rescheduled on short notice, which affected the conversion rate. ^ Part of a joint webinar series “Engaging with your community through events and training” between CORBEL and EOSC-Life. # Postponed due to the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic on the speakers’ agendas; expected to run before the end of the project.*

An additional 7 webinars were run in the context of the machine learning workshop and training of service providers in the use of ARIA for the Open Call.

Training courses

During this period, the CORBEL training programme organised 8 face-to-face courses. We provide a description of each course below. Other WPs in CORBEL have also delivered training courses and workshops, which are not specifically reported in this deliverable. Examples: WP5 held a training workshop on CORBEL/AARC AAI in Freising, Germany on 23-24th April 2018. It was co-located with ELIXIR AAI training for service providers (24-25th April 2018), this provided participants training from basic concepts of AAI to how to integrate new services to ELIXIR AAI.

Designing an awesome service (23 January 2018, Berlin)

WP9 delivered this training module as part of the WP4 Service Operators meeting. The focus of the workshop was: a practical introduction to user research and how it can inform training. It was a 4 hours training session with lectures and hands-on practicals on user experience design and user research techniques and how to create and describe a training event.

Impact

This workshop was created for CORBEL and is now actively implemented during the second day of the course *Managing a bioinformatics core facility*⁹ at EMBL-EBI and the *EMBO practical course Research to service - planning and running a bioinformatics core facility*¹⁰.

Instruct ULTRA/iNEXT ARIA Workshop: Introducing version 2 of ARIA with a hands-on workshop for facility managers and service operators

(2 February 2018, Amsterdam)

A one day event was delivered by Instruct-ERIC with a combination of lectures and hands-on sessions to introduce version 2 of ARIA. The workshop focused on how to manage access to research infrastructures using ARIA version 2. It started with an introduction to ARIA version 2 and the differences to the previous version and it included hands-on demonstrations about access, machine booking and notifications as well as a hands-on support session. Other topics covered in the workshop were how to get help with ARIA, other ARIA functions and future developments.

Train the trainer workshop & course development hackathon

(4-6 July 2018, Amsterdam)

CORBEL organised two events back to back about training and course development. Participants could attend both events or only one of them. The overall aim was to support trainers, educators,

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/2020/managing-bioinformatics-core-facility-0>

¹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/2019/embo-practical-course-research-service-planning-and-running-bioinformatics-core-facility>

training work package leaders and training coordinators by providing them with new ideas and tools to make their training events even better and easier to run and prepare.

The topics covered in each of the two events were:

Train-the-trainer course (4 & 5 July)

The workshop was led by the needs of participants with many practical exercises. The topics covered were:

- Training Design: How to optimally use didactics and method diversity
- “Turn manure into compost”: How difficult training situations can contribute to workshop success
- Moderating discussions and workshops
- Reading the room/gaining feedback
- Ensuring transfer of training into daily practice

Topics: course development hackathon (6 July)

During the hackathon on 6 July participants had the opportunity to integrate what they had learnt the two previous days into their current projects with additional input of their peers. The topics covered were:

- Examples of interactive training activities (flash talks)
- Exchange of experience with respect to training budget, best practices, marketing of training (depending on interest in the room)
- Protected time to work on your current projects and get advice from colleagues (brainstorming on concepts etc.)
- Get to know who is involved in training in the RIs with the aim of creating a network of people interested in training delivery

Participant feedback

After the course, participants received a feedback survey. 9 of them completed it, out of which 5 had attended both the Train the Trainer workshop and the course development hackathon. Most respondents rated the sessions as *Excellent* or *Good*, but one person rated them as *Average*. 7 (78%) people would recommend the course and the 2 others answered *Maybe* to that question. When asked about the best part of the course, respondents valued the possibility of sharing training experiences with others and learning from the discussions. Two respondents would have liked that the course had more explanations and scientific evidence and two considered that the part of the hackathon to work on your own project was not good if you did not have anything to prepare.

Machine learning for image analysis

(29-31 October 2018, Heidelberg)

Course overview (as advertised on the website)

This is a blended learning course on Machine Learning for Image Analysis, consisting of three online sessions with associated hands-on exercises prior to the workshop, a three day face-to-face workshop at EMBL Heidelberg and two optional online sessions with associated hands-on exercises after the workshop. The course is jointly organised by CORBEL, EMBL, German BioImaging and NEUBIAS (COST Action CA15124).

The course will be a great mix of intensive learning, extensive hands-on and community networking in the field of Machine Learning for Image Analysis.

Up-front online sessions: Participants will review the fundamentals of machine learning in three up-front webinars complemented by online tutorials. The webinars will take place on the 2nd, 9th and 16th October 2018, 12:00 - 14:00 but a recorded alternative can be provided.

On-site workshop: Next, they will apply their knowledge at an on-site workshop (EMBL Heidelberg, October 29-31), in small interactive groups (the workshop has 20 available seats and ~8 trainer/lecturer), to both reference datasets and their own data. Topics to be practiced in these groups include: 2D and 3D segmentation with convolutional neural networks, Content aware image restoration, simulation of ground truth data, labeling strategies and transfer learning. Participants will be asked to pick one group for the practical sessions.

Follow-up online sessions (optional): After the on-site workshop, two optional advanced training webinars, complemented by online tutorials, will be given on 9th and 16th November 2018. These will focus on simulation of data, transfer learning and boosting.

Audience

This course is aimed at both core facility staff and research scientists.

Prerequisites for this workshop are programming skills in Python and ideally Tensorflow, Keras or Pytorch as well as basic knowledge of machine learning theory.

Participants should provide an outline of one image analysis task that holds potential to be ideally solved with machine learning. Neural networks have been successfully applied to various medical and biological imaging modalities including PALM/STORM, light sheet fluorescence microscopy, high-throughput microscopy, electron microscopy, X-ray tomography. However, they require observation-outcome-pairs for training. Ideally, you will provide annotated images.

Learning outcomes

After this course you should be able to:

- Explain the fundamentals of machine learning methods suitable for image analysis
- Consult users/colleagues in strategies to obtain ground truth
- Give advice in training and using a neural-network
- Perform simple quality control on the results of one selected ML approach

Participant feedback

14 of the 22 course participants answered the feedback survey. They all rated the course as *Good* (38%) or *Excellent* (62%). During the on-site practical part of the course, they were divided into four groups working on different problems. They all rated the sessions they attended as *Good* or *Excellent*. All survey respondents would recommend the course. They will all use the tools they learnt about during the course in their future research. Participants to the course appreciated the possibility to work with their own data with the help of experts. 30% of respondents considered that the course was too practical and that future editions of the course could include some more theoretical background. Several commented that they would like the course to be longer, at least 4 days.

Impact

After this course was created as part of the CORBEL training programme in 2018, it has been adopted in the EMBL training programme and is still run in 2020, entitled *Deep learning for image analysis*¹¹. The feedback received in the 2018 edition was taken into account to develop this course.

Data Visualisation for Biology: a practical workshop on design, techniques and tools (11-15 March 2019 and 16-20 March 2020)

This is a 5-day course that runs at EMBL-EBI and is co-organised by CORBEL. After the edition in 2017 (included in D9.3 - CORBEL Pilot courses and staff exchange provided)¹², it ran again in 2019 and was planned to run in 2020, but it was in the end cancelled due to the COVID-19 outbreak. The course description, learning outcomes and programme were similar in both editions, but because of the feedback received after the edition in 2019, this year participants were going to be divided into 3 groups according to their experience and interest for the hands-on part of the course.

Participant feedback 2019 edition

22 participants responded to the course survey. Most of them rated the course as *Excellent* (25%) or *Very good* (60%) and would recommend the course (90%). 85% of respondents found the balance between theoretical and practical content to be *About right*. When asked about the best part of the course, they mentioned: the concepts of data visualisation on the first two days, the keynote speaker and the visualisations in D3. The most repeated answers for the worst part of the course were: the overlap between concepts taught on the first two days and the steep learning curve of D3. But there were also comments about the introduction to Javascript, because some participants already had experience in Javascript. This shows a difference in prior knowledge between participants. This was also shown in their additional comments at the end of the survey, where they suggested splitting the course into two workshops to find the right balance for everybody. It was also pointed out that the description of the course on the website did not reflect the content of the course and the programming knowledge required to follow the exercises.

2020 edition

The course content and the description on the website have been changed according to this feedback: the information about the course describes better what would have been taught during the course and participants would have been divided in 3 groups to avoid big differences in their prior expertise within the same group. Preparatory exercises were sent out so that participants could assess which group fits them better.

The information below is the one used to advertise the course on the website in 2020.

Course overview

As biological datasets increase in size and complexity, we are moving more and more from a hypothesis-driven research paradigm to a data-driven one. As a result, exploration of that data has become even more crucial than in the past.

In this 5-day course, we will dive into the topic of biological data visualisation and how it can be used to gain insight into and get a "feel" for a dataset, so that targeted analyses can be defined. We will start by covering theoretical questions such as: What is data visualisation? How do we perceive images? How can we visualise data in the best possible way? It will be delivered through a mixture of

¹¹ <https://www.embl.de/training/events/2020/MAC20-01/>

¹² <https://zenodo.org/record/1044177#.XkPphxP7TOQ>

lectures and workshop sessions, and will also provide hands-on experience in developing visualisations. The course will focus on working with omics (e.g. genomics, transcriptomics) data rather than e.g. imaging data.

Audience

This course is targeted at biologists who want to explore and gain further insight into their own data through the use of visualisation and design approaches. People with different backgrounds and previous expertise in data visualisation are welcome to join the course.

Some prior experience in programming would be beneficial, however participants will be divided into groups according to their programming experience for the hands-on element from day 3 onwards. Applicants will be asked to provide detail on their level of programming ability and knowledge of visualisation tools as part of the application process. Some pre-reading and exercises will additionally be sent out to successful applicants prior to the course, and these will also help us decide on the most appropriate groupings.

Learning outcomes

At the end of this course, trainees will be able to:

- Explore theories of perception and cognition
- Identify frameworks to comprehend data visualisation
- Explain the concepts of visual design process
- Implement visualisations with specific tools (either Vega-Lite or D3)

Preparations before the course

A set of tasks of increasing difficulty were sent to the accepted participants before the course. In this way, they could get an idea of the tools that would be used during the course and which group suited them best. From this, 9 people were identified as possible participants of the advanced group, run as a hackathon. A survey was sent out to these 9 people asking about possible projects for the course. 4 people replied to this survey with project suggestions for creating better visualisations of existing data and websites.

Course cancellation

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic in the beginning of 2020, we decided to cancel this course. We are discussing with the trainers the possibility of delivering part of the content remotely.

Aria workshop (25 February 2020, Amsterdam)

Overview

The workshop will be a series of talks that will give a background to the ARIA software and introduce some of its core features. We will be demonstrating the newly released features around visit and session management, including the financial reporting module developed in collaboration with EU-OPENSREEN. There will also be an interactive session for feedback and ideas gathering to help shape the future of ARIA.

Participant feedback

Participants gave a high rating to the course in the feedback survey: the average score was 4.42 out of 5. Most respondents would like that the workshop continues to run on a yearly basis. The most useful sessions were “Overall introduction to ARIA” and “Facility management live demo”. Participants in the workshop were researchers or facility managers; 21 from CORBEL and 24 from

iNEXT-Discovery and Instruct-ERIC. The key reasons for people to attend the course were: increased understanding of how to use ARIA, see future developments before they are released, and talk to developers about problems they are having.

Impact

This workshop ran before the start of the CORBEL project and will continue to run as part of EOSC-Life. CORBEL has contributed to keep the contents focused on the software and broad enough to attract participants from outside Instruct-ERIC, reaching about 50% of the workshop attendees.

Conclusion

CORBEL defined the competency requirements for technical operators of RIs and used this information to develop training. This competency profile is now available for anyone interested in the professional development associated with an RI or any training professional who wants to design courses in the same area or to build a similar competency profile for other communities.

The modular curriculum developed by CORBEL has strengthened the BMS RIs by training its professionals and contributing to exchange of best practice among them. Cooperation between RIs has increased as a consequence of the training & Staff programme and this will continue in the future. A number of training courses developed by CORBEL have been adopted into the training programme of the RIs (e.g. Innovation training in EATRIS), and a number of RIs now run their own webinar series (e.g. EATRIS, BBMRI-ERIC, ELIXIR) and have benefitted from the experience gained by the CORBEL webinar series.

Lessons learned

The collaboration between BMS RIs will continue in EOSC-Life, where all the RIs in CORBEL are represented. EOSC-Life will create an open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research. The mission of EOSC-Life is to make data resources “FAIR” and publish them in the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) following guidelines and standards.

EOSC-Life will organise training events, including workshops, hackathons and bring-your-own-data events to develop and share best practice to work in data-driven research. The training programme of EOSC-Life will see continued training on a number of training topics that featured in CORBEL such as Aria, FitSM and Quality Management. EOSC-Life also includes an OpenCall for training thereby allowing topics not previously planned for to continue.

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Adjustments made

None

Appendix

N/A